

Surgical and Non-Surgical Endodontic Strategies in the Management of Large Periapical Lesions: A Case Series

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Abstract

Conventional non-surgical endodontic therapy generally demonstrates high clinical success; however, surgical intervention may be required in certain situations. This case report describes a patient with periapical lesions in the maxillary anterior region. One lesion was treated through periapical surgery using a novel and safe technique to separate the soft tissue mass located close to vital and sensitive anatomical structures, while the other lesion was managed with long-term intracanal medicament. This highlights the importance of selecting treatment approaches based on the patient's best interest.

Keywords: Large periapical lesions, intracanal medicament, periapical surgery.

Introduction

Periapical lesions are a frequent pathological outcome of pulpal infection, mainly caused by bacterial invasion within the root canal system, which triggers inflammatory and immune responses in the periapical region¹. These lesions encompass periapical granulomas, radicular cysts, and periapical abscesses, with a reported occurrence of approximately 30% to 70% in teeth with necrotic pulps. The main objective of endodontic treatment is to eradicate infection, facilitate healing, and re-establish the integrity of periapical tissues. However, the management of large periapical lesions remains clinically challenging and often necessitates a tailored treatment strategy². In contemporary endodontic practice, the indications for periapical surgery have reduced considerably; however, it still constitutes approximately 3–10% of routine endodontic procedures³. This case report highlights that nonvital teeth associated with periapical lesions should initially be managed using conservative, non-surgical approaches, with surgical intervention reserved for cases where conventional treatment fails. Studies by Oztan and Kalaskar et al. have demonstrated that even large periapical lesions can respond successfully to non-surgical management

using calcium hydroxide paste^{2,3}. Cohn suggested that periapical surgery is a predictable treatment option when root canal therapy is either not feasible or unsuccessful. Therefore, surgical endodontic intervention is indicated in a limited number of cases involving persistent peri radicular pathology, and treatment decisions should be tailored to the specific clinical scenario, as illustrated in this report⁴.

Careful and complete removal of periapical granulation tissue is a critical component of surgical endodontic procedures. In cases involving large anterior maxillary cysts, surgical removal may lead to oro-nasal communication, particularly when the cyst has eroded the bony floor of the nasal cavity, leaving only a soft tissue barrier^{5,6}. To address such challenges, an innovative surgical approach has been introduced for the removal of periapical lesions, aiming to preserve adjacent vital anatomical structures while effectively managing pathology resistant to conventional treatment⁷.

This case report presents the management of two different maxillary periapical

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pathologies. A large “through-and-through” lesion involving both buccal and palatal bone loss was treated surgically using a novel lesion separation technique after failing to respond to intracanal medicament, whereas a smaller lesion was successfully managed with long-term intracanal medicament^{8,9}. To the best of our knowledge, such a presentation has not been previously documented in the literature.

Case Report

Case 1: Non-Surgical Root Canal Treatment in a 14-Year-Old male

Clinical and Radiographic Presentation

A 14-year-old male was referred to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of pain in the upper front tooth region for one month. Medical history and investigations did not reveal anything that could oppose or influence the proposed treatment plan. The patient gave a history of trauma to the teeth 10 years back.

On clinical examination, it was seen that the maxillary right central incisor (tooth no 11) was discolored and fractured. The teeth (#11) tested non-vital through cold test and electric pulp testing (Digitest, Farmingdale, NY). Tooth was tender to percussion. Periodontal examination revealed sulcus depths within normal limits. A preoperative radiograph and CBCT revealed a large periapical radiolucency and open apex associated with the affected teeth, and borders of tooth 12 was also involved indicating a periapical lesion of size approximately 11 mm with an intact cortical plate suggesting unilocular cystic lesion.

Treatment Plan

The patient underwent conventional non-surgical root canal treatment (NSRCT) with respect to tooth 11 and 12. The operative field was isolated, and access preparation was done on both the teeth without local anesthesia. After the radiographic determination of the working length, biomechanical preparation following the ‘step back’ method was done using 5.25 % sodium hypochlorite and normal saline as an irrigating agent. Triple Antibiotic Paste was placed as an intracanal medicament, and the root canal access was sealed with zinc oxide eugenol cement at the end of the first appointment.

After 15 days, Triple Antibiotic Paste is repeated as an intracanal medicament. The patient is recalled after 21 days. After 21 days, the patient reported relief from his symptoms. The tooth became asymptomatic, and radiograph showed progressive periapical healing. MTA was placed to seal the open apex in 11 and obturation was done with gutta-percha and sealer. Post obturation restoration was done using resin-modified glass ionomer liner as base followed by composite restoration in relation to #11.

Follow-Up and Outcome

The patient remained asymptomatic, and follow-up radiographs at 6, and 12 months showed progressive periapical healing. At the 12-month follow-up, complete bone regeneration was observed

FIGURE 1 A. Pre-operative radiograph, B Working length determination, C. MTA placed in the canal. D Master cone E Post obturation radiograph F. CBCT image. G Immediate post-operative clinical photograph H. Healing at 6 months follow up. I Complete healing at 12 months follow up.

CASE 2: Surgical Management of Failed Non-Surgical Root Canal Treatment in a 42-Year-Old male.

Clinical and Radiographic Presentation

A 42-year-old male presented with persistent pain and swelling in the maxillary central incisor region (tooth #21). Patient gave a history of trauma to the teeth 10 years back. A preoperative CBCT scan showed a large periapical lesion with an associated intraoral sinus suggested hypodense cystic

lesion of 14mm. Under proper isolation and anesthesia, a root canal treatment was performed. After 2 weeks the patient was still symptomatic with persistent radiolucency at apex in 21, hence, periapical surgery was planned.

Treatment Plan

Since the NSRCT failed, surgical intervention was planned, which included:

- Administration of local anesthesia (bilateral infraorbital nerve block, nasopalatine nerve block, and local infiltration) and full thickness mucoperiosteal flap elevation.
- Apicoectomy was done, and the pathology was removed, followed by curettage of the residual granulation tissue.
- The enucleated periapical lesion was stored in a 10% buffered formalin solution and sent for histopathological examination. The root resection was not done to maintain maximum cemental covering on the root surface and to maintain the original root length to help tooth stability. Gutta-percha at the exposed root apex was burnished.
- The bone cavity was irrigated with sterile normal saline and gently dried with moist gauze. Careful clinical and radiographic inspection of the area was done to ensure no residual lesion tissue was left behind.
- The flap was repositioned, and the flap margins were ensured to rest on sound bone. The flap was sutured using 5-0 silk with interrupted sutures.
- The patient was given postoperative instructions both verbally and in writing. Antibiotics, analgesics, and mouthwash were prescribed. Histopathological biopsy report confirmed the presence of granulation tissue.

Follow - Up

Patient was kept under follow up and recalled after 10 days for suture removal w.r.t 11. Healing was uneventful. Patient was recalled again after 1 month, 3 months & 6 months. Healing was seen to be satisfactory. Crown preparation was done and a permanent crown was cemented w.r.t 21.

Figure 2 A. Pre-clinical photograph, B. Pre-clinical radiograph, C. Working Length determination, D. Master Cone, E. Post -obturation radiograph, F. CBCT image showing cystic lesion G. Flap elevation H. Removal of the pathology and Curettage of bony crypts. I.Suture placement J. 6 months follow up K. 1 year follow up L. Post operative clinical photograph after prosthesis.

Discussion

A conservative (nonsurgical) approach is preferred for treating periapical lesions, as they usually result from inflammation caused by bacterial infection within the root canal. Nonsurgical root canal therapy focuses on cleaning and disinfecting the canal system, reducing bacterial load, and allowing healing of periapical tissues.¹⁰ Therefore, surgical intervention is reserved for selective cases where the cause lies inside the root canal, such as persistent microorganisms in periapical tissues, cysts, or foreign body reactions. In the present case, surgery was considered to prevent tooth loss because the left maxillary anterior region did not respond to conservative treatment.

The cases of large periapical lesions were managed initially with conservative treatment using calcium hydroxide as

an intracanal medicament. After 21 days, the left tooth in case 1 became asymptomatic and showed healing, while the left tooth in case 2 remained symptomatic, requiring surgical intervention due to pathology beyond the root canal.¹¹

Calcium hydroxide aids periapical healing by eliminating residual bacteria, reducing inflammation, dissolving organic debris, and preventing microleakage. In this case, it was effective on the left side but failed on the right, where infection persisted in the periapical tissues^{12,13}.

Conventional curettage carries risks of damaging vital structures. Hence, a modified technique using sterilized gauze and gentle lateral pressure was employed to separate and remove the lesion safely. This blunt approach minimized tissue injury, ensured complete removal, and improved surgical outcomes.

Follow-ups at 6 months and 1 year showed asymptomatic teeth with radiographic healing, indicating successful treatment.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that using calcium hydroxide as an intracanal medicament in endodontic treatment is an effective method for promoting periapical healing in nonvital teeth with periapical lesions. However, when such lesions do not respond to this approach, periapical surgery becomes necessary. Additionally, a novel surgical technique was introduced in this case to manage large periapical lesions while minimizing the risk of damage to surrounding vital structures.

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